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Use Of Social Media Tools For Effective Learning Of Business Education In Tertiary Institutions In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the use of social media tools for effective learning of Business Education in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The area of social media tools examined were social media tools required for learning of business education, the extent of availability of social media tools for learning business education, also considered was the extent of utilization of social media tools in learning of business education among others. Consequently, the moderating influence of gender and type of institution were examined. Two research questions were raised and answered, and Two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 1006 Business Education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The sample size was 201 using simple random sampling technique. The instrument used was a structured questionnaire and was validated by three experts. The Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient (PPMC) was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument and reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-test Statistics. The findings of the study revealed that social media tools such as Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram, YouTube, Google, Skype, and Teacher Tube are required in learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State and that social media tools utilization in learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State is to a low extent. It was therefore, concluded that social media tools such as Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram, YouTube, Google, Skype and Teacher Tube are required for the learning of business education and that these social media tools are available to a high extent. However, the utilization is to a low extent. Based on the findings, it was recommended that Business Education students should ensure that they utilize other social media platforms apart from WhatsApp and Google in learning of business education

Keywords; Use of Social Media, Effective Learning, Business Education

INTRODUCTION

The competitive nature of service delivery in educational system has recently improved due to the invert of social media. Social media platforms have completely changed the way learning activities are coordinated through effective communication tools. Social media are online networking process accessible to a vast number of people, and have emerged as a major instruments for interpersonal connection over the years. The use of social networking sites, the acceptances and access to new learning opportunities are made possible by learning. The primary concerns around social media

shows networking identity, network infrastructure, privacy, technological challenges, and the necessity of using it as a learning tool (Arnold, & Paulus, 2010).

Users of social media tools can disseminate and exchange knowledge via network provider. These platforms or apps can have many users or very few social media followers. The sites which include, Facebook, Instagram, Tik Tok, Twitter, WhatsApp, and others enable students to interact and communicate with one another. Along with the aforementioned information, researchers claimed that a larger portion of these active users are students, supporting the theory that students use online networking sites primarily and actively. Their rise has had a profound effect on both the students are taught. The affordances of social engagement, content sharing, and content production on these platforms are the features that worry us. Most importantly, students who could not meet in person during the pandemic were able to accomplish their task outside the classroom (Robbins. 2014).

As a result, several approaches to doing things that are very different from the traditional methods have been made possible by technological advancements. These advancements in growth have led to the emergence of social networking and media. There has never been as much social interaction as there is in the present-day. The widespread use of educational mobile technology in online learning, especially at higher institutions, has gained momentum recently, especially in industrialized nations. This allows students more options and opportunities when it comes to online instruction (Sharpe, 2016). Everyone has embraced social media and networking, especially "WhatsApp," one of its tools. Young people in particular have accepted it more than others. Without a question, young people in Nigeria are involved in online communities. Numerous educational establishments in Nigeria and other part of the universe can vouch that most students have smartphones and actively participate in digital society.

Social media tool is a combination of educational-based applications which permits its users to create contents, share videos, audios and allows interactions with multiple user's same time. Some of this tools that allows easy sharing of information includes, Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp, Facebook, Google, YouTube, Instagram, Pinterest, Websites, etc. According to Sivakumar (2020), social media plays an important part in the process of acquiring knowledge and it is gradually gaining ground especially among students of higher institution. Strenger(2013) as cited by Okoro (2020), maintained that social media is important in order to provide communication among individuals regardless of the distance .

Employing Twitter (now known as X), Facebook, WhatsApp and YouTube for example has enhanced the learning of students especially in business education field, these tools enable students develop independent mental capacity, and these students are able to digest the lecturer's explanations using informal settings, self-orientation and timespan . The Facebook for instance, is universally accessible, convenient and also flexible with knowledge and information hence, helping these students gain easy access to these information, videos and audio needed to perform their teacher's task connecting to their learning contents thereby leading better understanding. Facebook covers networking site to communicate with follow course mate, lecturers and other members (Akpojotor. 2022).

Again, Emojevwe (2020) who found that Twitter, WhatsApp, Tik Tok, Instagram, YouTube, Zoom, Google, Skype, and Teacher Tube are required in learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Midwestern State.

Onlinya, Kanu and Nwandu (2024) who found that Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, Google plus Instagram, Snapchat, LinkedIn, Pinterest, Blogger, are some of the social media platforms available for the learning of business education.

Ukata and Nmehielle (2021) who found that e-learning resources for learning are available and utilized but at a low level in polytechnics in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

In today's digital society, success in education and other spheres of activities is attributed to effective use of information and communication technology (ICT). Higher education cannot be spared from these rapidly evolving technological advancement. Today's academics have been technologically savvy and proactive users of ICTs, recently students have been very much interested in using various social media sites for communication. The youth who are the proactive users of these social media platforms uses the site to connect friends, photos and games. While some researchers claim that the use of digital online sites by students enhances student learning. Morgan, Graham & Hodges 2012) It

has been observed student no longer take their studies seriously, this is because they may be busy chatting with friends and acquaintances on Facebook, Instagram, whatsapp instead of using social media tool for learning activities. Also, many students do not take cognizance of their vocabularies when communicating using social media tools. They engage in using slangs and abbreviations against using the right words and spellings, they end up transcending these slangs into their learning activities which also leads to too many grammatical errors in education. The need for proper measure to be taken to avoid this unpleasant situation has led to this study investigating the use of social media tools for effective learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to investigate the use of social media for effective learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Specifically, the study sought to:

Determine the social media tools required in the learning of business education in tertiary Institutions in Delta State.

Determine the extent of availability of social media tools in the learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research questions was raised to guide the study

1. What are the social media tools required in learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State?
2. What is the extent of availability of social media tools in learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance which guided the study.

1. There is no significant difference between mean rating of male and female business education students on social media tools required in the learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
2. There is no significant difference between mean rating of male and female business education students' on extent of availability in tertiary institution in Delta State.

Theoretical Framework

Social Learning Theory (SLT) is useful for explaining how social media impacts students' behavioral tendencies to use online learning tools. This theory is grounded in both behavioral and cognitive theories. According to Bandura (1977), SLT illustrates how behavior can be acquired from the environment through modeling, including concepts such as reciprocal determinism, observational learning, and facilitation. Bandura also suggested that people learn new behaviors and their functional value by observing others. Yoon, and Tourassi (2014) further supported this idea, stating that observing others in the environment can influence one's thinking. SLT can be broken down into three key components: psychological determinants of behavior, observational learning, and environmental determinants of behavior.

RESEARCH METHOD AND PROCEDURE

The study adopted the correlational descriptive survey design. This implies that survey gathers information about variables of study not individuals responding to instrument. The researcher examined the opinions, attitudes or feelings of individuals about a particular problem.

The population of the study is made up of 1006 Business Education students from 2022/2023 academic session which is comprised of 304 students from Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba and 76 students from University of Delta, Agbor in Delta State respectively 347 students from Delta state university, Abraka, 123 students from College of Education, Warri and 156 students from College of Physical Education, Mosogar

The sample for this study consisted of 201 respondents, which is 20% of targeted population from the institutions under review. The simple random sampling method was employed to select 20% of the population, which gave 201 as sample size for the study. The simple random sampling method was used to enable generalizations about a specific population and leave out any bias; and makes room for

inferences and predictions to be made about a population to survey or collect data from every individual in that population.

The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled: Use of Social Media Tools for Learning of Business Education Questionnaire (USMTLBEQ) developed by the researcher. It was a 48-item questionnaire containing two sections; each dealing with items. It has sections A and B. Section A is meant to elicit data on demographic variables while Sections B is meant to elicit data on the independent variables. A four-point rating scale was used to measure and calculate responses of respondents. Respondents were to tick (√) one of the four options on the scale as Strongly Agree (SA=4) Agree (A=3) Disagree (D=2) Strongly Disagree (SD=1) or Very High Extent (VHE=4), High Extent (HE=3), Low Extent (LE=2), and Very Low Extent (VLE= 1)

The validity of the research instrument was determined by three experts, two in the Department of Business Education and one in measurement and evaluation unit, at Delta State University, Abraka. Their constructive criticisms were used to improve and prepare the final copy of the instrument.

The copies of the instrument were administered to 20 Business education students of University of Benin which were not part of the population for the study. Using the test-retest method a reliability coefficient 0.82 was obtained. The researcher visited each of the sampled institutions and administered the research instrument to the respondents in the various Business Education Departments with the help of five research assistants, one from each of the institutions. The research assistants were properly briefed on purpose of the study, questionnaire distribution and collection. All the 201 questionnaire distributed were retrieved, making it a 100% return rate.

The mean was employed in answering the research questions while and standard deviation was used to determine the homogeneity of the respondents' ratings. The decision was based on the grand mean in relation to the boundary mean score of 2.50. A grand mean that is equal to or above 2.50 means agreed or high extent while the one with mean score less than 2.50 was disagreed or low extent. t-test was employed to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was retained when the calculated value was equal to or greater than the significant level of 0.05 and rejected when the calculated value was less than the significant level of 0.05.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What are the social media tools required in learning of Business Education in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.1: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of Business Education students on social media tools required in learning of Business Education

S/N	Statement Items	X	SD	Remark
1.	Twitter	2.90	1.20	Agree
2.	WhatsApp	3.20	0.86	Agree
3.	Instagram	2.64	0.48	Agree
4	Youtube	2.60	0.84	Agree
5.	Facebook	2.17	0.66	Disagree
6.	Google	3.56	0.50	Strongly Agree
7.	Skype	2.66	1.06	Agree
8.	LinkedIn	2.12	1.33	Disagree
9	Pinterest	2.24	0.98	Disagree
10	Teacher Tube	3.00	0.39	Agree
	Grand Mean/SD	2.71	0.83	Agree

Source: Field work (2024)

Data presented in Table 4.1 revealed the mean responses of Business Education students on social media tools required in learning of Business Education. The result showed that the respondents strongly agreed to item 6 with a mean of 3.56 and a standard deviation of 0.50. Also, they agreed to six of the items (ie. items 1, 2, 3, 4, 7 and 10) with mean ranged from 2.60 to 3.20, and standard deviation ranged from 0.39 to 1.20. They however, disagreed to three of the items in the scale (items 5, 8 and 9) with mean ranged from 2.12 to 2.24. The standard deviation ranged from 0.66 to 1.33. Similarly, the grand mean of 2.71 depicted that social media tools such as Twitter, WhatsApp,

Instagram, YouTube, Google, Skype, and Teacher Tube are required in learning of Business Education in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Also, the grand standard deviation of 0.83 depicted that the respondents were not far apart in their responses.

Research Question 2: *What is the extent of availability of social media tools in learning of Business Education in tertiary institutions in Delta State?*

Table 4.2: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of Business Education students on extent of availability of social media tools in learning of Business Education

S/N	Statement Items	X	SD	Remark
1.	Twitter	2.99	1.09	High Extent
2.	WhatsApp	3.59	0.49	Very High Extent
3.	Instagram	2.83	0.76	High Extent
4	Youtube	2.76	0.68	High Extent
5.	Facebook	2.78	0.67	High Extent
6.	Google	3.00	0.77	High Extent
7.	Skype	2.13	0.65	Low Extent
8.	LinkedIn	1.99	0.64	Low Extent
9	Pinterest	1.95	0.27	Low Extent
10	Teacher Tube	2.54	0.95	High Extent
	Grand Mean/SD	2.66	0.70	High Extent

Source : Field work (2024)

Data presented in Table 4.2 portrayed the mean responses of Business Education students on extent of availability of social media tools in learning of Business Education. The result showed that the respondents agreed to a Very High Extent the availability of WhatsApp in learning of business education with a mean of 3.59 and a standard deviation of 0.49. They equally agreed to a High Extent to six of the items (ie. items 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 10) with mean ranged from 2.54 to 3.00, and standard deviation ranged from 0.49 to 1.09. Also, the respondents agreed to a Low Extent to three of the items in the scale (ie. items 7, 8 and 9) with mean ranged from 1.95 to 2.13 and standard deviation ranged from 0.27 to 0.65. Similarly, the grand mean of 2.66 depicted that social media tools such as Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram, YouTube, Facebook, Google, , and Teacher Tube are available in learning of Business Education in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Also, the grand standard deviation of 0.70 showed that the respondents were not far apart in their responses.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between mean rating of male and female Business Education students on social media tools required in the learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Table 4.3: t-test Analysis of male and female business education students on social media tools required in the learning process of business education.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	α	t	p-value	Decision
Male	77	2.92	1.20	199	0.05	0.22	0.84	Not Significant
Female	124	2.89	1.20					

Table 4.3 showed that t-value of -0.20 at 199 degree of freedom with a p-value of 0.84 is greater than the criterion value of 0.05(0.84 > 0.05). Since p-value is greater than the significant value, the null hypothesis is therefore retained. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Business Education students on social media tools required in the learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between mean rating of universities and colleges of education business education students’ on availability of social media tools in learning of Business Education in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Table 4.4: t-test Analysis of male and female business education students on availability of social media tools in learning of business education

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	α	t	p-value	Decision
Male	77	3.08	1.12	199	0.05	0.95	0.34	Not Significant
Female	124	2.93	1.08					

Data presented in Table 4.4 showed that the t-value of 0.95 at 199 degree of freedom with a p-value of 0.34 is greater than the criterion value of 0.05 ($0.34 > 0.05$). Since p-value is greater than the significant value, the null hypothesis is therefore retained. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Business Education students on availability of social media tools in learning of business education in tertiary institutions in

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study on research question one indicated that social media tools such as Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram, YouTube, Google, Skype, and Teacher Tube are required in learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The finding agreed with the findings of Emojevwe (2020) who found that Twitter, WhatsApp, Tik Tok, Instagram, YouTube, Zoom, Google, Skype, and Teacher Tube are required in learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Midwestern State.

The findings on research question two showed that social media tools such as Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram, YouTube, Facebook, Google and Teacher Tube are available in learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State to a high extent. This findings is in harmony with the findings of Onlinya, Kanu and Nwandu (2024) who found that Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, Google plus Instagram, Snapchat, LinkedIn, Pinterest, Blogger, are some of the social media platforms available for the learning of business education. This findings contradicts the finding of Oyenike (2021) who found that social media are not adequately available in Colleges of Education in South-South, Nigeria.

The result of hypothesis one showed that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Business Education students on social media tools required in learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State. This is in line with Akanbi and Anyio (2014) who found in their study that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the availability usage of social media.

The result of hypothesis two showed that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female Business Education students on availability of social media tools in learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State. This finding corroborated with the findings of Akpojotor (2022) who found that there was no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female business education lecturers on the department’s digitalization prospects. Also the findings agreed with that of Oyenike (2021) who found that male and female business education lecturers were not significantly different in their ratings regarding availability of social media in Colleges of Education in South-South, Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that social media tools such as Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram YouTube, Google, Skype and Teacher Tube are required for the learning of Business Education and that these social media tools are available to a high extent. However, these social media tools are only utilized to a low extent in tertiary institutions in Delta State. Also, that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female business education students on extent of utilization of social media tools in learning of business education in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the afore-mentioned result of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The management of tertiary institutions should ensure that they provide sufficient fund for the business education department to enable them to purchase data for their internet service required for social media platforms.
2. The Head of Department of Business Education should always ensure that social media tools are available in the departmental computer room for students to make use of.
3. The business Education students should ensure that they utilize other social media platforms apart from WhatsApp and Google in learning of business education.

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